

Feedback Report on the Workshop on Academic Writing and Research Skills and Meet the Expert: at Sudur Paschimanchal Academy

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Event Overview

The Workshop on Academic Writing and Research Skills was organized by Sudur Pashchimanchal Campus from July 31 to August 2. The program was presided over by Mr. Puspa Raj Joshi, the former campus chief, and featured Prof. Dr. Padam Raj Joshi, the Dean of the Management Faculty, as the Chief Guest. The workshop was led by Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra, a distinguished researcher and trainer. <https://www.facebook.com/spacollege> dated August 2, 2024

<https://fb.watch/tO1AOttNJb/>

<https://fb.watch/tO1CH7hENL/>

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Key Highlights

- **Engagement and Participation:** The workshop saw active participation from students and faculty, fostering an interactive environment conducive to learning. Participants expressed enthusiasm for the topics covered and were eager to apply the skills learned.
- **Content and Delivery:** Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra delivered insightful sessions on academic writing, research methodologies, and effective communication strategies. His expertise provided participants with practical tools to enhance their research capabilities. Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra's recent discourse provide valuable insights into various aspects of research methodology, academic writing, and the formulation of research problems. His work emphasizes the importance of structured approaches to research and the critical elements that contribute to effective research outcomes.

Key Insights

Research Consumer: In his publication titled "Research Consumer," Mishra (2024) discusses the role of consumers in the research process, highlighting how understanding the needs and preferences of research consumers can enhance the relevance and applicability of research findings. This insight is crucial for researchers aiming to align their work with the expectations of stakeholders.

Research Problem Formulation: Mishra (2024) emphasizes the significance of clearly defining research problems as the foundation of any research project. A well-formulated research problem guides the direction of the study and helps in identifying appropriate methodologies and frameworks for investigation.

Hypothesis Development: In "Hypothesis in Research," Mishra (2024) outlines the process of developing hypotheses, stressing that a strong hypothesis is essential for guiding research design and analysis. He provides practical examples of how to formulate testable hypotheses that can lead to meaningful conclusions.

Research Methods: Mishra (2024) provides a comprehensive overview of various research methods, discussing qualitative and quantitative approaches. His insights encourage researchers to select methods that best fit their research questions and objectives, thereby enhancing the validity and reliability of their findings.

Research Writing: In "Research Writing Exercise," Mishra (2024) offers practical exercises aimed at improving academic writing skills. He emphasizes the importance of clarity, coherence, and organization in research writing, which are vital for effectively communicating research findings to a broader audience.

Research Report Preparation: Mishra (2024) outlines the essential components of a research report, including the introduction, methodology, results, and discussion sections. He stresses that a well-structured report is critical for conveying research outcomes and facilitating further research in the field.

Sampling Techniques: In "Sampling in Research," Mishra (2024) discusses various sampling techniques and their implications for research outcomes. He highlights the importance of selecting appropriate sampling methods to ensure that research findings are representative and generalizable.

Introduction to Business Research Methods: Mishra (2024) provides an overview of business research methods, emphasizing their relevance in addressing real-world business challenges. This publication serves as a valuable resource for students and professionals seeking to apply research methods in business contexts.

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra's discourse to the field of research methodology and academic writing are invaluable for both emerging and established researchers. His emphasis on structured approaches to research, clear problem formulation, and effective communication of findings enhances the quality and impact of academic work.

- **Feedback from Participants:**

- Many participants reflected on the nostalgic feelings associated with their academic journeys, emphasizing the importance of simplicity and tactfulness in research.
- Suggestions included the need for a boot camp-style approach to streamline research efforts and enhance productivity.
- Participants discussed the relevance of poverty-related research methodologies and the importance of managing teaching hours to allocate more time for research activities.
- **Collaborative Learning:** The workshop encouraged collective learning through group discussions and WhatsApp groups for ongoing collaboration. Participants highlighted the value of sharing knowledge and resources with peers to foster a supportive academic community.
- **Creative Approaches:** The idea of transforming challenges into creative opportunities was a recurring theme, with participants discussing how to utilize available resources effectively.
- **Future Directions:** The workshop concluded with a call to action for participants to share what they learned with colleagues and to engage in further research initiatives. The importance of continuous learning and adaptation in academic writing and research was emphasized.

Conclusion The Workshop on Academic Writing and Research Skills was a resounding success, providing valuable insights and practical skills to participants. The collaborative atmosphere fostered a sense of community and encouraged ongoing engagement in research activities. Moving forward, it is recommended that similar workshops be organized regularly to continue supporting the academic growth of students and faculty at Sudur Pashchimanchal Campus.

Recommendations for Future Workshops

1. **Follow-up Sessions:** Organize follow-up workshops to reinforce skills learned and address any challenges participants may face in applying these skills.
2. **Mentorship Programs:** Establish mentorship programs pairing experienced researchers with students to provide guidance and support in their academic endeavors.
3. **Resource Sharing:** Create a centralized platform for participants to share research resources, articles, and tools that can aid in academic writing and research.
4. **Focus on Practical Applications:** Include more hands-on activities and real-world applications of academic writing and research skills to enhance learning outcomes.
5. **Feedback Mechanism:** Implement a structured feedback mechanism to gather insights from participants on future workshop topics and formats.

This feedback report aims to encapsulate the essence of the workshop and provide constructive suggestions for future improvements.

References

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Moderator: Mr. Jagan Nath Joshi is an accomplished academician with over 22 years of teaching experience. He currently serves as an Assistant Professor and the Head of the Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC) at Sudur Paschimanchal Campus. In addition to his teaching responsibilities, Joshi is the Managing Editor of SP: SWAG journal, a publication dedicated to scholarly work.

Throughout his career, Joshi has demonstrated a strong commitment to education and research. His extensive experience in the field has allowed him to make significant contributions to the academic community. As the IQAC Head, he plays a crucial role in ensuring the quality and continuous improvement of the institution's educational processes.

Joshi's dedication to his work is evident in his role as the Managing Editor of SP: SWAG journal. In this position, he oversees the publication of scholarly articles and research papers, promoting the dissemination of knowledge and fostering academic discourse.

With his impressive teaching experience and leadership roles, Jagan Nath Joshi continues to make a positive impact on the educational landscape. His commitment to excellence and his contributions to the field of academia are commendable.

Resource Person: Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra is a distinguished scholar with a Doctorate in Project Management from Kanpur University, where he focused on Project Performance Assessment in Terms of Time, Cost, and Quality of Bridge Construction Projects. He also holds a post doctorate in Operational

Analysis of Projects in Nepal. He is further doing his D.Litt on Safe Building Project Operation as highest academic research degree. Currently, Dr. Mishra serves as a Professor at Kathmandu College of Management, United Technical College. He is a regular visiting faculty, thesis supervisor, and research professor at various institutions, including Myaglung Campus Teraththum Institute of Engineering, Puichowk, Dharan, Lumbini Engineering, Gaurishanker Campus, Apex College, Srinivas University and Lincoln University and Management Science College, Rupandehi. Dr. Mishra has held positions as an associate professor and research director at Joint Constituent College of Pokhara University. He is the Editor-in-Chief of DV Publication, India, and serves on the editorial boards of several journals published by colleges in Nepal. Additionally, he is a member of various scientific societies, such as the South Asia Institute of Science and Engineering (SAISE), Fellow of the SAS Society, Member of the Operation Research Society of Nepal, and Country Coordinator of the International American Council for Research and Development (IACRD). Dr. Mishra's expertise has been recognized through numerous awards and honors bestowed by national and international organizations. He has published 17 international reference books and has been a chief guest, organizer, speaker, and advisor for various conferences. He holds 25 Intellectual Property Rights from the Government of India and 6 patents including United Kingdom and India. With an impressive publication record of over 200 peer-reviewed research articles, Dr. Mishra has presented at 15 international conferences and numerous national conferences. He supervises theses for universities such as Lincoln University, Malaysia, Srinivas University, India, and Tribhuvan and Pokhara University of Nepal. He serves as an external examiner for research work at various universities and as a keynote speaker at local and international conferences. Dr. Mishra's research projects are supported by governmental and private organizations in Nepal. He is an advisory board member of different international journals published by universities. Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra's commitment to occupational safety, sustainability, and development project management has been instrumental in driving progress and innovation in these critical areas. His research and contributions have left an indelible mark on the industries and communities he has served, making him a respected and influential figure in his field.

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra's impactful research made him to represent AD Scientific index as **best management scientist in Nepal**.

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1. Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=en&user=70NJhYAAAAAJ>
2. ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Anjay-Mishra>
3. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2803-4918>
4. SSRN: <https://privhq.ssrn.com/submissions/MyPapers.cfm?partid=3255631>
5. Global Peace Challenge: https://globalpeacechallenge2020.org/peace_ambassadors/dr-anjay-kumar-mis

